

Application of Nanotechnology in Textile Industry: A Review

Sayoni Nath & Anirban Dutta

Government College of Engineering and Textile Technology Serampore, W.B., India

Abstract:

Nanotechnology is considered as one of the most promising and emerging technologies for the 21st century. Nano Science along with the nanotechnology encompasses the study and application of very small and tiny things which can be used across all the other science fields such as physics, chemistry, biology, material-science and engineering. This technology overcomes the drawbacks of applying traditional methods to impart certain properties to textile materials. Nanotechnology applied in smart textiles has modernized the textile world. Fabric touch pads, bullet free jumpsuits, invisible coating and advance fibers turned the basic textiles into smart textiles. The use of nanomaterial and nanotechnology-based processes are growing at a tremendous rate in all fields of science and technology. In this context, the use of nanotechnology in textile industry has also increased rapidly due to its unique and valuable properties. Nanotechnology has versatile applications in textile chemical industry in manufacturing garments with stain resistance, wrinkle resistance, finishes, antibacterial qualities, UV Protection etc. The future success of nanotechnology in textile applications lies in area where new principles will be combined into durable, multifunctional textile systems without compromising the inherent textile properties. In this present review paper, the present applications, principles and future scopes of the nanotechnology in the field of textile and apparel manufacturing have been discussed as a complete overview.

Keywords: *Anti-static, E-textiles, Nano-composite, Nanomaterials, Nanotechnology, UV-Protection*

*Corresponding Author:

Dr. Anirban Dutta

Government College of Engineering and Textile Technology

12, William Carey Road, Dist, Serampore,

Hooghly - 712 201, W.B.

E-mail: speak.2.anirban@gmail.com

1. Introduction

Nanotechnology (NT) is the specific field of technology which deals with particles of the length of 1-100 nm. At the molecular level, nanotechnology can be applied for imparting the required textile features, like self-cleaning, antimicrobial characteristics, fire retardancy, hydrophobicity, durability, soft and smooth surface-feel, remarkable surface texture, high tenacity etc. [1].

Nanoparticles, nanofluids, nanowires and nanofilms all have incredible potential for the applications in the different domains of science and technology i.e. microbiology, optics, electronics, textiles, biomedical, coatings, aerospace, materials science, energy, plastics and mechanics etc. It is established that the ordinary conventional materials treated with nanoparticles show significant improvements in certain physical, mechanical and chemical properties owing to large surface area of nanoparticles. A remarkable improvement in desired properties has been reported while moving from microscopic to nanoscopic. Nanoparticles contributes in upgradation of some unique properties by precise and controlled arrangements of molecules and atoms [2].

Advances in nanotechnology for the textile industry have initiated the special and emerging field which paved the way for several potential and opportunities for the textile industry. All of these are highlighted in brief in this review paper. This paper's main focus is on summarization and consolidation of nanotechnology's recent applications as they relate to textile and apparel products.

In this context, it can be stated that beyond just fulfilling the basic human needs of protecting and covering the body, the textile-fabric now can be developed with some specific characteristics for some special and unique applications in our daily life. For example, static protection, self-cleaning, shrink resistance, stain resistance, fire - resistance, electrical conductivity, fragrance release, UV protection, water repellent (hydrophobic), moisture

management, high strength, antimicrobial and wrinkle resistance by the controlled application of nanotechnology [3]. The salient advantages of nanotechnology is based on the nanostructure, nanoscale additives, nanoscale thin membranes, engineered nanomaterials and nanoscale transistors etc. Materials that can engineered by nanotechnology is reported to be more durable, sieve like, lighter in weight, conductive, stronger and may possess many other uniqueness [3].

Nanotechnology is used in the process of imparting certain functional characteristics to the textiles, which includes self-cleaning fabrics, dye capability enhancement, flame retardation, UV and anti-static protection. The latest nanotechnology-based wrinkle free treatment is launched by Nano-Tex which provides enhanced performance while preserving the integrity and strength of the fabric, offering an alternative to the harsh traditional process. Nanotechnology makes the current applications work more efficiently and effectively as it is an enabling technology. A great Scope in the future is possessed by the nanomaterial due to their potential of being used for various advanced applications in numerous sectors [1]. Nano fabrics are textiles engineered with small particles that imparts advantageous properties such as super-hydrophobicity, odor moisture elimination, increased elasticity, bacterial resistance to the ordinary textile materials. Depending upon the desired property, a nano-fabric is either constructed from nanoscopic fibers called nanofibers or ordinary textile fabric treated with nano-particles [4]. The most common nanomaterials in clothing are nano-silver and nano-titanium-dioxide. Nano-silver is woven into fabric to give it anti-bacterial properties, to repel the bacteria that make those clothes smell badly after sweat. Nano-Titanium dioxide also adds sun protection to clothing just as it does in sunscreen creams. It can be said strongly that, Nanotechnology is increasingly attracting worldwide attention because it is widely perceived as an option offering huge potential in a wide range of end uses. The unique and new properties of nano-materials have attracted not only scientists or researchers but also business personnels, due to its huge economic potential [5]. The use of nanotechnology in textiles can allow for the control of crystal structure, improved mechanical properties, improved resistance to adverse external factors, electrical properties and self-cleaning features of clothing [6]. Furthermore, textiles can be nano-engineered to have specific functions including hydrophobicity, antistatic behavior etc. And most importantly, using nanotechnology these properties can be achieved without compromising with breathability, wear comfort and tactile comfort of textile materials [7].

Apart from imparting certain specific properties to the apparel fabric, the nanotechnology has a great role to play in the fields of smart-textile as well. Smart textiles are a type of sensitive and responsive materials that can sense and respond to the change in physical and mechanical properties of the surroundings, i.e. they can respond to change in magnetic, mechanical, electrical, thermal or chemical parameters. In modern days, the smart textiles are being used in various fields i.e. health care, IOT-based health-monitoring, environment, military and hygiene etc. [8]. Smart textiles are manufactured as composites and coatings that result in sensor materials or wireless data transmission. It is possible to impart smartness in textile materials to be used as sensors or auto-responsive elements by treating with of nanoparticles, nanofilms and nano-coatings. Moreover, it is very much possible to achieve improved electrical conductivity, high mechanical strength and thermo-stability by the application of nano-particles [8, 9].

2. Review of Literatures

Available review paper of Ali K Yestisen et.al. [10] provides a fair understanding about the nanoparticle and its application in imparting some significant properties like stain repellence, wrinkle resistance, static elimination, electrical conductivity to fibers without compromising their comfort and flexibility. Also, the available papers are very much insightful about the application of smart garments that can sense and respond to external stimuli via electrical, color or physiological signals. Moreover, this review paper provides a fair understanding about the electronic and photonic nanotechnology that are integrated with textiles and shows their applications in displays, sensing, drug release within the context of performance, durability and conductivity. Also, it throws some light regarding some risk factors including nanotoxicity, nano material release during washing, environmental impact of nanotextiles based on life cycle assessments. Furthermore, this available article reports an analysis of nanotechnology consolidation in the textiles market to evaluate global trends including some insight about the present limitations of nanotechnology in the textile industry [10].

In this context, another article reports the application of nanotechnology with the materials of 1 to 100 nm in length [11]. This paper provides a fair understanding about the physical, chemical and biological properties of the nano particles. The Figure 1 represents a pictorial comparison of different categories of fibers in terms of diameter-range along with corresponding technologies.

Figure 1: Fiber size and associated Manufacturing process [11]

In addition to that, this paper is very much insightful about the high tensile strength of nano particles, unique surface structure, soft-hand, durability, water repellency, fire retardancy and antimicrobial properties. [11]. The Figure 2 represents a consolidated pictorial view of different functional applications of nano finish for textile fabrics.

Figure 2: Fabric finishing for enhanced properties and performances [11]

Furthermore, another very relevant paper [2] reports about the application of nano-particles in medical textiles, which includes the development of artificial muscles which are used to match biological muscles. This paper is very much insightful about the use of fabrics treated with silver nano-particles (AgNPs), for the development of most effective antiseptic bandages or dressings. This paper provides a fair understanding about the encapsulation and piezoelectric properties of the nano particles. Also, it enlightens about the deformation-detection, light transmission, sensing and data transmission device for smart applications in the field of Internet of Things (IOT). In addition to that, it provides a fair understanding about the phase change material (PCM) and the features of thermostat. The application of nano technology in case of military purpose to monitor the stress and failure in human body during combat conditions is also reported. Also, it is insightful about the application of nylon nano particles which are utilized as protective clothing for the filtration applications and the application of fiberglass and carbon nano tubes which are widely used in the air filtration industry. The application of nano technology in smart textile and sportswear is also highlighted [2].

The applications of nano-finishes for medical purposes is also reported by the researchers. In this context, silver is very crucial element in biological point of view. It has been used in bio-treatment since ancient past. It is evident that the Silver has natural anti-fungal and anti-bacterial features. The nanotechnology has a great role to play in this domain as well. Polyester non-woven and colloids treated with nano-silver particles possess enhanced anti-bacterial properties. Resistance to bacterial growth in nano-silver particles makes it suitable to be applied in some special apparels like socks. Also, these nanoparticles are widely used in gauge or bandage materials for the purpose of wound, scald and burn dressings. Electrostatic, thermal and padding methods are utilized to apply nano-finishes on textiles. Textiles are generally treated with silver nanoparticles through padding technique. Also, antimicrobial filters are produced by manipulation of antimicrobial agents (Ag with nanofibers). Many nanofiber membranes like cellulose, PAN, (polyacrylonitrile) and PVC (polyvinyl chloride) containing Ag nanoparticles are found to be possessing antimicrobial properties. Engineered nanomaterials containing Ag and Ag⁺ nanoparticles are used as antimicrobial filters with sufficient transport properties [2, 12].

Apart from Ag nanoparticles, titanium oxide and magnesium oxide nanoparticles are also utilized as biological protective agents. Also it is reported that, nanoparticle finishes can convert a material into sensor based material. Such sensors can be effectively used for IOT-based health monitoring systems. For instance, piezoceramic particles that are incorporated into the textiles can sense the pulse and heart beat by conversion of mechanical force into electrical signals. It is further reported by the researchers that Zinc oxide and titanium oxide nanoparticles are used for oxidative catalysis, UV protection and fiber protection. And also, the Silicon dioxide and aluminum oxide nanoparticles with polypropylene or polyethylene coatings are utilized as super waterrepellent purposes. It is further evident from the available researches that the ceramic nanoparticles are also being developed for enhanced abrasion resistance. Nanoparticles of indium tin oxide are used as infra-red protective clothing. Applications of Nylon fiber containing zinc oxide particles are found to enhance the antistatic and shielding effect [2].

Also, another article [13] reports the application of nano technology in the manufacture of the multi-functional textiles with sustainable durability which can be integrated into smart textiles. This paper provides a fair understanding about the use of interactive textiles which can perceive and response to external stimuli to align themselves with changes in the surrounding environment. This paper is very much insightful about the self-cleaning and self-healing ability of the nano particles. Moreover, it focuses on the application of the adjunctive garments that can response to the external stimuli. This review addresses the broad highlights of modern textile in the realm of smart application of nano technology to improve our daily life efficiency [13].

Furthermore, the article [14] in this context conveys that the use of nano materials and nano technology-based process are growing at a tremendous rate in all fields of science and technology. This paper is very much insightful about the application of nano technology in the textile industry that has increased rapidly due to its unique and valuable properties. Also, it provides a very clear and fair understanding about the use of nano technology in the apparel industry in manufacturing of garments with special functional properties like stem resistance, wrinkle resistance, wrinkle-free finishes etc. This paper is very much insightful about the anti-bacterial properties of nano particles and UV protection [14].

It is evident from available researches that metal-oxide nanoparticles can be effectively used for protection of skin from UV radiations. In this category, Titanium oxide, magnesium oxide, zinc oxide and aluminum oxide are the commonly used metal oxides that possess the potential of UV absorption, photocatalytic, electrical conductivity and photo-oxidizing capability [2, 15, and 16]. Also, nanotechnology can be used for protection against toxicity. Nanoparticles of above-mentioned metal oxides work against the biological and chemical toxic agents. It is evident that zinc oxide and titanium oxide nanoparticles are most popularly used as UV resistance elements [2, 17-20].

Regarding the application procedures, the Silver-nanoparticles coated on cotton fibers through pad dry cure method exhibited high laundering durability, retaining the antibacterial properties and anti-fungal properties against many pathogens even after several washing cycles. Such durability of silver-nanoparticles has made it a very effective and popular choice for the application on textile materials [2, 21].

Moreover, the Organic or inorganic titanium-oxide and titanium-dioxide have significant impacts on certain special features of textiles i.e. photo stabilizing wool, super-hydrophobic, photo-catalyst, co-catalyst for cotton crosslinking, antibacterial, gas sensor, self-cleaning, hydrophilic, dye degradation and solar cell. Also, the carbon nanotubes are utilized as chemical absorbers, electrically conductive device, antistatic, antimicrobial, and fire retardant. Furthermore, in this category, clay nano-particles used as UV absorber, antibacterial and flame retardant. In this context, it is also reported that the gold nanoparticles are electrically conductive and effective antibacterial agents [2, 21-24].

It is further reported by the researchers that the nylon nanofibers coated with silver has excellent antibacterial properties against gram negative E.coli and staphylococcus aureus bacteria. Also, the Electrospun nylon 6 nanofibers coated on cotton/nylon woven fabrics has effective filtration property. By using nylon-6 nanofibers, it is reported that around 99.5% efficiency is achieved without any surrendering in pressure drop and loss in air permeability [2, 25, and 26]. It is also found that Nylon fabric treated with electrospun nanofibers using the nanoparticles of ZnO, SrTiO₃ and TiO₂ exhibits significant self-cleaning features. It has been proved by characterization techniques that fabrics treated with such nylon (polyamide66) nanofibers retaining high photo

activity after repeated wash and dye degradation [2, 12, 27, 28].

In this domain, another report [29] conveys the application of nano-science and nano-technology which encompasses the study and application of very small things and which is popularly used in the other science fields such as physics, chemistry, biology, Material science and Engineering. This paper provides an effective understanding about multifunctional textile structures, breathability and flexibility of nano particles. Also, it enlightens about the drawbacks of traditional process to impart certain properties to textile materials [29].

Another research paper [30] in this context, presents the use of nano dimensional silicon dioxide which may be used for final treatment of cotton and polyester textile materials in the process of industrial and household washing of the textile products. Furthermore, the insightful knowledge is available about the application of nano-materials on hygroscopicity, moisture yielding capacity, humidity, anti-soiling property and permeability. In addition to that it is very much insightful about the properties of textile materials with different fiber compositions after the nano-treatment [30].

Also, critical review is available [31] regarding the influence of the various types of the nano-finishes on the functional properties of the fabrics. This paper is very much insightful about multifunctional properties of the nano particles. In this context, Figure 3 represents the SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope) images of Zinc-Oxide (Zno)nano-particles on different textile materials.

Figure 3: SEM Images of ZnO nano particles on A-Polyester before washing and B-Cotton after washing [31]

This article [31] conveys clearly about the application of Titanium di-Oxide nano particles which have been applied on the cotton fabrics to improve their wrinkle resistance. Silver-Oxide nano particles have been found to be best suited for imparting antimicrobial resistance and also in the treatment of wounds resulting from burns. This paper provides a significant insight about the use of polymer nano composites. Also, this paper is very insightful about the application of zinc oxide nano particles which have been used in stain elimination of textiles [31].

In this context, Figure 4 represents fabric cross-sections of different nano-finished fabrics.

**Figure 4 : A and C: Fabric cross-section with Anti-bacterial nano-treatment
B and D : fabric samples finished with mixed nano-particles TiO₂/nano-Ag (2.0 wt%/125ppm) [31]**

In this regard, reports are obtained [32] about the application of nano technology for multiple purposes of the textile industry. This paper is very much insightful about the nano-treatment for water repellency, wrinkle resistance, UV-protection, anti-bacterial properties without alternating the other mechanical properties. This paper is insightful about the stability of application of nano materials on textile which has a key role in determining the success of nano textiles economically and sustainability for environmental safety [32].

The Table-1 represents different types of nano-materials for different types of functional-finishes of the textile substances, as obtained from different research papers and review papers

Table-1: Different nano-materials for different functional finishes on textile

End-use requirement	Suitable nanomaterials	References
Protection from UV	ZnO, TiO ₂	2, 17-20
Improved staining and fade reduction	Nanoporous hydrocarbon, Carbon black, SiO ₂ matrix	2, 18, 33
Moisture absorbency	TiO ₂	2, 17
Self-cleaning properties and water repellency	TiO ₂ , Fluoroacrylate, CNT, SiO ₂ matrix	2, 34-35
medicinal products or fragrances	Montmorillonite (nano clay), SiO ₂ (as matrix)	2, 36
Antistatic and conductive	Carbon nanotubes (CNT), Carbon black, Copper, Polypyrrole, Polyaniline	2, 37-38
Durability	Metal oxides like Al ₂ O ₃ , SiO ₂ , ZnO, CNT, Polybutylacrylate	2, 17
Antibacterial	Chitosan, Ag, SiO ₂ matrix, ZnO and TiO ₂	2, 17-18
Fire proofing	Boroxosiloxane, CNT, Montmorillonite (nano clay), Sb ₃ O ₂	2, 35

Also, another article [39] reports about the unique and new properties of nano materials. This paper mainly focuses on the improvement of the nano-applications. This paper effectively throws some light in the domain of the application of nano-particles in the fields of color change, UV radiation, textile heating etc. In this context, Figure 5 represents the schematic diagram of a very special technique of treating synthetic fiber with nano-touch wrap.

Figure 5: Schematic representation of a Nano-Touch treated fiber [39]

Likewise, the Figure 6 represents the 3D simulation of the application of nano-set of nano-dry on synthetic fibers.

Figure 6: The Schematic representation of the 3D Molecular nano-net of nano dry [39]

Also, this paper is very much insightful about the economic potential of the nano particles. Moreover, it conveys effective information about the applications of nano-technology in the fields of high-tech fibers, stay-clean textiles and antistatic textiles [39]. Also, this paper provides a very vivid and effective pictorial representation of the change of surface with the change of the particle size at nano-scale, which is self-explanatory (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Schematic representation of particle size and surface at nano scale [39] .

There is a specific and special need of protection and comfort in adverse and extreme environments. Increased performance efficacy and unique functionality are the prime and crucial objectives to tackle the emergency and adverse situations, specifically in case of defense and security purposes. Nano-materials can be used to design special jumpsuits that can be used as low GSM bullet-proof textiles. These jumpsuits can be used in battlefields to detect and monitor injuries, health issues and pulse rate. Also, the conductive polymers that are embedded onto woven textile fabrics, worked as chemical sensors. These are engineered to monitor and detect health-hazards like toxic gases etc.

Application of Carbon nanotubes (CNT) as fillers in different polymers for imparting and enhancing different mechanical, heating and chemical properties of polymers are discussed by researchers. Also, Carbon-nanotube based polymer-composites are used as sensors of different external factors like pH, gasses, temperature, pressure, chemical vapors, light, strain and liquid. Also, the carbon doped polymers are used as piezoelectric materials, which can be effectively used as stretch actuators [40]. For high performance textiles, sensing apparels are made by the combination of carbon black powder and silicone. In case of modern-day electric-blankets, carbon-doped polymers can

be used as reported by the researchers. Now it is possible to produce conductive textiles by incorporating the carbon-based fabrics [2, 40].

Coatings on the textiles are mainly used to obtain high performance and enhanced functionality. On the other hand, CNTs coatings are used presently on textiles for sensing applications. For example general cotton yarns are converted into e-textiles by coating of carbon nanotubes. Basically, polyelectrolyte-based coating of carbon nanotubes is carried out on the cotton yarns. Presently, it is possible to detect the blood protein (albumin) with the help of CNTs coated cotton yarns. Not only on the threads/ yarns, but carbon nanotubes can be coated on the fabrics and polymers as well. They may be utilized as lithium-ion battery [2, 41]. Development of self-powering energy textile was also reported that transforms solar energy into electrical energy using CNTs [42]. Another report was found which studied carbon-activated cotton threads on textile also for energy generation [2, 43].

Nanotechnology is an emerging and fast-growing interdisciplinary technology often seen as an element of industry 4.0. Nanotechnology (NT) involves the dealings with particles of 1 to 100 nm in length. The fundamentals of nanotechnology are based upon the fact that the basic properties of materials drastically alter when their dimensions are reduced to nanometer scale. In recent time the textile industry has adapted nano-technology, in different domains of applications, in both research level and commercial level. So, it can be stated that nanotechnology in textile is the realization, manipulation, and control of matter at the nano-length, such that the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the materials (individual atoms, molecules, and bulk matter) can be engineered, synthesized and altered to develop the next generation of upgraded materials, devices, structures and systems. It is used to develop desired textile features such as high tenacity, high tearing strength, durability, engineered surface structure, soft and smooth hand-feel, water repellency, fire retardancy, antimicrobial properties, self-cleaning, medical applications, thermoregulation properties etc.,

The application of nanotechnology makes the current processing work more efficient and effective. A great opportunity and potential of nanotechnology in the future can be forecasted due to their potential of being used for various advanced applications in a number of sectors. Also, it has gained commercial success as the companies are focused on the production of the nano-textile products, including conventional characteristics and meeting international safety, health, and environmental standards too. It can be said with a lot of affirmation that this technology is steadily finding its way into textiles for a long time now.

Moreover, textile-based nano-sensors are also being developed by the companies, thus opening numerous options for the nano-textile, including the creation of smart-clothes that easily adapts and responds accordingly to the weather changes, and also real-time monitoring of the vital physiological signs of the wearers, and customized healthcare systems. It can be of a huge interest in the field of IOT-enabled smart apparels also,

On the other hand, so far as the limitations or challenges are concerned, it is reported by the researchers that nanotechnology failed after the first trial for health care application, due to its poor medical consistency at reasonable price range. So, presently, the main focus of the commercial application of nanotechnology is presently on life style-regulation. Major thrust is towards the sportswear applications [2]

It is further reported that the textile and apparel companies and research organizations are presently working in collaborations to find out and formulate the unique ways of evaluating, sharing and tracking the athletic performance of the sportspersons using nanotechnology enabled sensors. However, it is obvious that aesthetic is the prime focus in the fashion industry. Therefore, commercial application of smart textiles are quite difficult [2]. Another drawback related to nano-finish and nanomaterials is the threat of toxicity. To evaluate the toxicity of engineered nanomaterials different methods are formulated. Also, the evaluation standards like IEC/TC113 and ISO/TC229 etc. have been prepared to measure the toxicity of nanomaterials. However, no distinct or defined resource is presently available to know about specific adverse effects of nanotechnology in textiles, or how it can be minimized. Some risks associated to engineered nanomaterials have been reported in the literature [2].

Some of the present researches reported the risks and potential hazards associated with the engineered nanomaterials that are used for facial cosmetics and textiles. The toxicity and other characteristics of engineered nanomaterials as projected through mathematical modelling are available in different literatures. However, at the same time, it is also reported that almost 90 % of nanoparticles of silver and other engineered nanomaterials can be eliminated by waste water treatment [2, 44-46].

But it must be noted that there is always a risk while using engineered nano materials like silver and zinc compounds. As, there is always a chance that engineered nanomaterials may be coupled with the large sized particles and then released into the atmosphere. For example, the Nano Titanium dioxide is the part of engineered magnetic materials that may cause harm to the organic cellular structures like lungs, brains etc. Nanoparticles can enter more easily into the lungs and may cause tissue damages [2, 44-46].

Although, more researches are needed to be carried out to gather more precise understandings about the potential adverse effects of the engineered nanomaterials. However, it is remarkable that some researchers have examined the sustained toxicity of engineered nanomaterials [2, 47].

Presently, there are a lot of uncertainties to assess the hazardous impacts of engineered nanomaterials on human health. As per the available researches it is found that there are quite a different types of engineered nanomaterials which have not caused any serious effects after exposure with skin. The bottom-line is that it is essential to have thorough and detailed investigations about the risk factors associated with nanomaterials, before its commercial and mass-scale applications. As it is highly recommended by all the world community of researchers [2][44-46]. Finally, In spite of all these shortcomings, it can be said that there is a paradigm shift of textile and apparel industry towards technological upgradation and modernization by the application of nanotechnology, even though it has some drawbacks and sustainability issues at present [2, 48-50].

3. Conclusion

There are lots of functional advantages of the application of engineered nanomaterials on textile fabrics. The particle sizes of certain materials like silver, zinc, titanium compounds etc. when reduced to the nano-level, possess remarkable characteristics and potential, which can be capitalized for enhancement of some functional and surface properties of textile materials. Wrinkle resistance, UV protection, water resistance, antimicrobial property, anti-static property, surface smoothness, thermo-regulation, self-cleaning property, durability etc. can be improved by the application of nano-finish. Also, application of engineered nano-materials in the fields of smart-textiles, e-textile, medical textile and technical textile are remarkable.

However, at the same time, it is associated with some drawbacks and threats as well, as the toxic influences of the nanoparticles on the environment and human health are of serious concern and still vast researches are to be carried out to have more precise guidelines for most optimized and favorable usage of Nano-materials. In addition to that, the high expenditures that are associated with the nanotechnology-based textile finishes is one of the biggest hurdles in the expansion of nano-textiles. For instance, In the apparel market, a common domain of interest is thermos-regulated or temperature-regulated clothing, however, customers stay away due to the hefty prices.

In spite of these temporary drawbacks and challenges, it is very loud and clear that a broad number of qualities are possessed by nanomaterials despite some cons, making the textile products extremely durable, lighter and stronger, and also giving them special end-use properties. The researches project a very promising and commercially successful future of nanotechnology in the textile industry, as it is evident that the quality and service must overcome the cost-barrier in the consumer market.

References:

- [1] Arslan Safder, "Use of Nano Technology in Textile Industry and its future", (June, 2022), [cited 13th Dec 2023] <https://nanografi.com/blog/use-of-nanotechnology-in-textile-industry-and-its-future/#:~:text=Nanotechnology%20is%20used%20in%20the,are%20explained%20shortly%20among%20them>
- [2] Hassan BS, Islam GMN and Haque ANMA, "Applications of Nanotechnology in Textiles: A Review", *Adv. Res Text Eng.*, Aug 2019; 4(2): 1038, Available online at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335193255_Applications_of_Nanotechnology_in_Textiles_A_Review
- [3] Ngô C, Van de Voorde MH. "Nanotechnology for the Textile Industry", In *Nanotechnology in a Nutshell*, Atlantis Press. 2014; 321-329
- [4] "Nano Fabrics", Wikipedia [cited 14th Dec 2023], <https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nanofabrics>
- [5] Tarver-Wahlquist, S., Rysavy, T F., Floyd, A., "The trouble with nano particles in Clothing", *Green America*, [cited 14th Dec 2023], <https://www.greenamerica.org/detox-your-closet-search-less-toxic-clothes/trouble-nano-fabrics>
- [6] Karst, D., & Yang, Y., "Potential advantages and risks of nanotechnology for textiles", *AATCC Review*, 6(3), 44-48, (March, 2006), Available online at: <https://experts.nebraska.edu/en/publications/potential-advantages-and-risks-of-nanotechnology-for-textiles>

- [7] Ali K. Yetisen, Hang Qu, Amir Manbachi, Haider Butt, Mehmet R. Dokmeci, Juan P. Hinstroza, Maksim Skorobogatiy, Ali Khademhosseini, and Seok Hyun Yun, "Nano technology in Textiles", *ACS Nano*, 10, 3, 3042–3068, (February, 2006), Available online at: <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/10.1021/acsnano.5b08176>
- [8] Syduzzaman M, Patwary SU, Farhana K, Ahmed S., "Smart Textiles and Nano-Technology: A General Overview", *J Textile Sci Eng*. 2015; 5: 181
- [9] Mudasir Akbar Shah, Bilal Masood Pirzada, Gareth Price, Abel L. Shibiru, Ahsanulhaq Qurashi, "Applications of nanotechnology in smart textile industry: A critical review", *Journal of Advanced Research*, Volume 38, 2022, Pages 55-75, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jare.2022.01.008>
- [10] Ali K Yestisen, Hang Qu, Amir Manbachi, 'Nano Technology in Textile', (February, 2006), [cited 14th Dec 2023] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/296055764_Nanotechnology_in_Textiles
- [11] A.P.S. Sawhney, B. Condon, K.V. Singh, S.S. Pang, G. Li, and David Hui, "Modern Applications of Nanotechnology in Textiles", *Textile Research Journal*, Volume 78, Issue 8, (August, 2008), Available online at: <https://doi.org/10.1177/0040517508091066>
- [12] Gopal R, Kaur S, Ma Z, Chan C, Ramakrishna S, Matsuura T., "Electrospun nanofibrous filtration membrane", *Journal of Membrane Science*. 2006; 1: 581-586
- [13] Tharwat I. Shaheen, "Nano technology in modern textiles", *The Journal of the Textile Institute*, (August, 2021), [cited 13th Dec 2023] <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/00405000.2021.1962625?journalCode=tjti20>
- [14] Barr, P., (2017), "Nano technology in modern textile era", *The Pharma Innovation Journal*, 6(10): p 287-288, (September, 2017), Available online at: <https://www.thepharmajournal.com/archives/2017/vol6issue10/PartD/6-10-10-331.pdf>
-
- [15] Sudheesh Kumar PT, Lakshmanan VK, Anilkumar TV, Ramya C, Reshmi P, Unnikrishnan AG, etc., "Flexible and microporous chitosan hydrogel/nano ZnO composite bandages for wound dressing: *in vitro* and *in vivo* evaluation", *ACS applied materials & interfaces*. 2012; 5: 2618-2629
- [16] Newman MD, Stotland M, Ellis JI., "The safety of nanosized particles in titanium dioxide–and zinc oxide–based sunscreens". *Journal of the American Academy of Dermatology*, 2009; 4: 685-692
- [17] Burniston N, Bygott C, Stratton J., "Nano Technology Meets Titanium Dioxide", *Surface Coatings International Part A*. 2004; 4: 179-184
- [18] Wong YWH, Yuen CWM, Leung MYS, Ku SKA, Lam HLI. "Selected applications of nanotechnology in textiles". *AUTEX Res. J.*, 2006; 1:1-8
- [19] Kathiervelu SS., "Applications of nanotechnology in fiber finishing", *Synth.Fibres*, 2003; 32: 20-22
- [20] Yang HY, Zhu SK, Pan N., "Studying the Mechanisms of Titanium Dioxide as Ultraviolet-Blocking Additive for Films and Fabrics by an Improved Scheme", *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2003; 92: 3201-3210
- [21] Balakumaran MD, Ramachandran R, Jagadeeswari S, Kalaichelvan PT., *In vitro* "Biological properties and characterization of nanosilver coated cotton fabrics—An application for antimicrobial textile finishing.", *International Biodeterioration & Biodegradation*. 2016; 107: 48-55
- [22] Rai M, Yadav A, Gade A., "Silver nanoparticles as a new generation of antimicrobials", *Biotechnology advances*. 2009; 1: 76-83
- [23] Saravanan R, Khan MM, Gupta VK, Mosquera E, Gracia F, Narayanan V, etc." ZnO/Ag/CdO nanocomposite for visible light-induced photocatalytic degradation of industrial textile effluents", *Journal of colloid and interface science*, 2015; 452: 126-133
- [24] Fernández-García M, Rodríguez J A., "Metal oxide nanoparticles". *Encyclopedia of Inorganic and Bioinorganic Chemistry*. 2011
- [25] Coyle S, Wu Y, Lau KT, De Rossi D, Wallace G, Diamond D., "Smart nanotextiles: a review of materials and applications.". *MRS Bulletin*. 2007; 05:434-442
- [26] Zohoori S, Karimi L, Ayaziyazdi S., "A novel durable photoactive nylon fabric using electrospun nanofibers containing nanophotocatalysts". *Journal of Industrial and Engineering Chemistry*, 2014; 5: 2934-2938
- [27] Romo-Urbe A, Arizmendi L, Romero-Guzmán ME, Sepúlveda-Guzmán S., Cruz-Silva R., "Electrospun nylon nanofibers as effective reinforcement to polyaniline membranes". *ACS applied materials & interfaces*. 2009; 11: 2502-2508
- [28] Park HS, Park YO., "Filtration properties of electrospun ultrafine fiber webs". *Korean Journal of Chemical Engineering*. 2005; 1: 165-172
- [29] A.K.M Ayatullah Hosne Asif, Md. Zayedul Hasan, "Application of nano technology", *International Journal of Engineering and Technology Sciences*, (January, 2018) [cited 12th Dec 2023] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323860395_Application_of_Nanotechnology_in_Modern_Textiles_A_Review
- [30] Daria Matveitsova, Olga Paraska, Svitlana Karvan, "Developing Compositions based on nanoparticles for final treatment of textile materials", (October, 2016), [cited 13th Dec 2023] https://www.researchgate.net/publication/309902156_Developing_compositions_based_on_nanoparticles_for_final_treatment_of_textile_materials
- [31] Narayanan Gokarneshan, Gopalakrishnan, B. Jeyanthi, (2012), "Influences of Nano Finishes on the Functional Properties of Textile Materials", *International Journal of Basic Applied Sciences*, 2(2): p8-24, (April 2012) Available online at:

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/339486552_INFLUENCE_OF_NANO_FINISHES_ON_THE_FUNCTIONAL_PROPERTIES_OF_TEXTILE_MATERIALS

- [32] Radhika –Damuluri, V.Kavitha Kiran, Damuluri P Chakravarthy, “Review Studies on application of nano technology in textiles”, Researchgate, (October 2017)
- [33] Song XQ, Liu A, Ji CT, Li HT. “The effect of nano-particle concentration and heating time in the anti-crinkle treatment of silk.”. *J. Jilin Inst. Technol.*, 2001; 22: 24-27
- [34] Lei Q, Juan PH., “Application of nanotechnology for high performance textile”. 2003; 1-8
- [35] Zhang J, France P, Radomyselskiy A, Datta S, Zhao J, Ooij WV., “Hydrophobic cotton fabric coated by a thin nanoparticulate plasma film.”, *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, 2003; 88: 1473-1481
- [36] Harholdt K., “Carbon Fiber, Past and Future.”. *Ind. Fabric Prod. Rev.*, 2003; 4: 14-28
- [37] Dong WG, Huang G., “Research on properties of nano polypropylene/TiO₂ composite fiber”. *J. Textile Res.*, 2002; 23: 22-23
- [38] Sennett M, Welsh E., “Dispersion and Alignment of Carbon Nanotubes in Polycarbonate”, *Appl. Phys. A.*, 2003; 1: 111-113
- [39] Kathirvelu Subramanian, L.D Souza, Allhaarathi, “Overview of Nano technology application in textile”, Researchgate, (May 2008) [cited 10th Dec 2023]
- https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289312334_Overview_of_nanotechnology_applications_in_textiles
- [40] Zhang R, Deng H, Valenca R, Jin J, Fu Q, Bilotti E, etc., “Carbon nanotube polymer coatings for textile yarns with good strain sensing capability.”, *Sensors and Actuators A: Physical*. 2012; 179: 83-91
- [41] Ravi S, Vadukumpully S., “Sustainable carbon nanomaterials: Recent advances and its applications in energy and environmental remediation.”, *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*. 2016; 1: 835-856
- [42] Pan S, Lin H, Deng J, Chen P, Chen X, Yang Z, etc., “Novel wearable energy devices based on aligned carbon nanotube fiber textiles”, *Adv. Energy Mater.*, 2015; 5: 401-438
- [43] Kim BH, Barnhart BS, Kwon JW. , “Electrostatic power generation using carbon-activated cotton thread on textile”, *Micro and Nano Systems Letters*. 2015; 3: 1-7
- [44] Som C, Wick P, Krug H, Nowack B., “Environmental and health effects of nanomaterials in nanotextiles and facade coatings.”, *Environment International*. 2011; 6: 1131-1142
- [45] Etzel RA, Balk SJ., “Pediatric environmental health”, *AAP Books*. 2011
- [46] Oberdörster G., “Safety assessment for nanotechnology and nanomedicine: concepts of nanotoxicology”, *Journal of internal medicine*. 2010; 1: 89-105
- [47] Ramesh GVR, “Research and Review: Nanotechnology in textiles”, *Journal of Pharmaceutics and Nanotechnology*. 2016; 2: 1-7
- [48] De Rossi DE, Paradiso R., “Future direction: e-textiles. In *Wearable Monitoring Systems*”, Springer US. 2011; 147-162
- [49] A.K.M. Ayatullah Hosne Asif and Md. Zayedul Hasan. “Application of Nanotechnology in Modern Textiles: A Review”, *International Journal of Current Engineering and Technology*, Vol.8, No.2 (March/April 2018) 227-231, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.14741/ijcet/v.8.2.5>
- [50] Mourad Krifa, Cambry Prichard, “Nanotechnology in textile and apparel research – an overview of technologies and processes”, *The Journal of the Textile Institute*, Feb 2020, 111(2):1-16, DOI: 10.1080/00405000.2020.1721696